

A Case for Nonparametrics and Alternatives

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Recently, teaching nonparametric approaches was illustrated by a challenging data example which was analyzed using a related R-shiny app [1]. In their discussion section they raise several questions, particularly ... *Since we have rejected the null hypothesis, we conduct pairwise Dunn's tests and compute pairwise Dunn's confidence intervals as a posthoc procedure' needs some clarification. Which value has a global test conditionally before multiple comparisons? Is the Kruskal-Wallis test an appropriate test?, Is the Dunn test appropriate?.* Particularly, Mood's median test and Kruskal-Wallis-test (KW) are compared to ANOVA F-test.

Case studies are well suited for teaching statistical assumptions, models, interpretations and software-based evaluation. The choice of the Bracht et al. 2016 data [2] is appreciated, because in this randomized clinical trial an unbalanced pseudo one-way layout for the continuous endpoint 'biomarker MFAP4' is used, where heterogeneous variances, skewness and even shape effects can already be seen from the boxplots overlaid with raw data, related to the treatment effects:

Figure 1: Hepatic fibrosis trial (Bracht et al. 2016 data): boxplots (males and females are characterized by boxes and triangles)

The factor 'stage of fibrosis' with the levels no fibrosis (stage 0), mild fibrosis (stage 1), moderate fibrosis (stage 2), severe fibrosis (stage 3), and cirrhosis (stage 4) is specific since the objective of the trial

is the differentiation of no to moderate (0-2) and severe fibrosis to cirrhosis (3-4).

First, this means that a global test (ANOVA, KW, median test) cannot answer the experimental question. It is also not suitable as a pre-test, neither conditional nor unconditional before the so-called post-hoc tests, simply because of the argument of differently defined H1 [4]. There are two possibilities i) to construct a joint test with these global tests using the closed testing procedure [13] or ii) using multiple comparison procedures (MCP) (inappropriately called post-hoc tests). Both ways allow the desired determination of the treatment comparisons of interest: as adjusted p-values or (mostly compatible) simultaneous confidence intervals (particularly easy for MCP). Is the MCP formulated as multiple contrast test, a maximum test $t_{MCT} = \max(t_1, \dots, t_h)$ based on single contrast tests $t_{Contrast} = \sum_{i=0}^h \xi_i \bar{y}_i / S \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^h \xi_i^2 / n_i}$ with specific contrast coefficients ξ_i^h , step contrasts are suitable for the above experimental question. Here in the example (didactically simplified for a balanced design in the upper part of the table):

ξ_i	S_0	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4
ξ_1	-1	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
ξ_2	-0.5	-0.5	0.333	0.333	0.333
ξ_3	-0.333	-0.333	-0.333	0.5	0.5
ξ_4	-0.25	-0.25	-0.25	-0.25	1
ξ_1	-1	0.3955	0.3034	0.1506	0.1506
ξ_2	-0.3553	-0.6447	0.5019	0.2491	0.2491
ξ_3	-0.2377	-0.4314	-0.3309	0.5	0.5
ξ_4	-0.2042	-0.3705	-0.2842	-0.1411	1

Table 1: Step contrasts for $h = 5$ stages S_i in both an assumed balanced and existing unbalanced design

Second, the question arises which test to choose given suspected, possibly treatment-dependent variance heterogeneity, skewness, and shape effects. Decision trees constructed from different pre-tests and conditional main tests to be selected are problematic and not recommended [10]. So one chooses robust tests or tests which are sensitive to all these distributional effects: explicit like the multi-model procedures [8] or implicit like the most likely transformation (MLT) [9]. To answer the primary experimental question confidence intervals and/or adjusted p-values for step contrasts are considered [3]: 1) a nonparametric approach for the relative effect size (NP) which is robust against variance heterogeneity (what the KW test is not) [12]), 2) a nonparametric approach for quantiles, namely medians [14], 3) a multi-model maximum test including Wilcoxon, Ansari-Bradley and Savage scores (MM) [8] and 4) the most likely transformation approach (MLT) [7]. The Appendix below contains the related R-code for the four procedures using the Bracht et al. 2016 data. For the location effect, all p-value are < 0.0001 , therefore three test statistics (NP, MM, MLT) are compared in Table 2:

Item	Step contrast	NP: test	NP: p-value	MLT: test	MLT: p-value	MM: test	MM: p-value
location	$[S_0 - (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4)]$	6.08	< 0.0001	5.96	< 0.0001	5.88	< 0.0001
	$[(S_0, S_1) - (S_2, S_3, S_4)]$	10.25	< 0.0001	9.13	< 0.0001	9.50	< 0.0001
	$[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$	13.00	< 0.0001	10.58	< 0.0001	11.61	< 0.0001
	$[S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3) - S_4]$	10.88	< 0.0001	8.70	< 0.0001	9.59	< 0.0001
scale	$[S_0 - (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4)]$					0.85	0.977
	$[(S_0, S_1) - (S_2, S_3, S_4)]$					-0.72	0.991
	$[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$					-3.70	0.002
	$[S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3) - S_4]$					-3.30	0.010
shape	$[S_0 - (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4)]$					5.59	< 0.0001
	$[(S_0, S_1) - (S_2, S_3, S_4)]$					8.47	< 0.0001
	$[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$					10.30	< 0.0001
	$[S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3) - S_4]$					8.03	< 0.0001

Table 2: Test statistics and p-values for three procedures: NP, MM, MLT

All step contrast are in the alternative, most $[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$, i.e. severe fibrosis and cirrhosis differs from mild up to no fibrosis. The second approach is visualized as two-sided Fieller-type confidence limits for the ratio of medians in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Fieller-type confidence intervals for step contrasts

Again, the contrast $[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$, denoted as C3 is most in the alternative.

There is a widespread assumption that parametric tests are seriously non-robust to deviation from the normal distribution. Such data situations are often found, especially skewness, excess and discrete values. However, particularly linear forms of parametric tests, such as t-test or contrast tests, are relatively robust. On the other hand, variance heterogeneity, especially in inverse unbalanced design, can lead to significant level violation and/or power loss. This brought the authors [11] even for the two sample test to the impressive title 'the lesser of two evils'. In the k-sample case, there is an additional possible bias-'the worst of all devils'. Exactly when a high s_i with small n_i occurs in a non-relevant treatment group. Then the joint MQR estimator increases with the consequence that the p-values of comparisons of interest, although with normal variances, increase falsely ([5],[6]). Table 3 compared the standard errors (SE) and the test statistics (t) of the homogeneous and heterogeneous step contrast procedures:

Step contrast	HET:SE	HET:t	HOM:SE	HOM:t
$[S_0 - (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4)]$	0.90	6.21	1.22	4.57
$[(S_0, S_1) - (S_2, S_3, S_4)]$	0.94	7.96	0.93	8.05
$[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$	1.45	8.24	1.08	11.07
$[S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3) - S_4]$	2.00	6.17	1.42	8.72

Table 3: Parametric step contrasts: standard approach assuming homogenous variances (HOM) and sandwich estimator modified approach (HET)

Qualitatively, the decisions are the same. But the modified variant (HET) shows a clear lower value for the step contrast of interest $[(S_0, S_1, S_2) - (S_3, S_4)]$ - correctly taking into account the higher variances in S_3 and S_4 compared to S_0, S_1, S_2 , see Figure 1. That means, parametric tests are quite robust for non-net real data, if one uses the modification for heterogeneity of variance.

Summarizing, to select an optimal test for a given real data situation is difficult. One can write a most robust test a-priori in a protocol or follow a guideline. In the other, more common case, one should be aware of the different assumptions, robustness properties, interpretability.

Appendix

```
library(nparcomp) ##### Approach 1)
npcc<-mctp(MFAP~stage, data=Bracht, type ="Changepoint", alternative ="two.sided",
          asy.method = "mult.t", info=FALSE, correlation = FALSE)

library(mratios) ##### Approach 2)
medrat<-mcpqrct(Bracht$MFAP, Bracht$stage, p = 0.5,
type = "Changepoint", method = "Fieller")

library(multcomp) ##### Approach 3)
library(coin)
Bracht$AB<- ansari_trafo(Bracht$MFAP, ties.method ="mid-ranks")
Bracht$SA<-savage_trafo(Bracht$MFAP, ties.method ="mid-ranks")
Bracht$RMFAP<- rank_trafo(Bracht$MFAP)
mod2<-lm(RMFAP~stage, data=Bracht)
mod3<-lm(AB~stage, data=Bracht)
mod4<-lm(SA~stage, data=Bracht)
Joint3 <- glht(mmm(location = mod2, scale= mod3, shape=mod4), mlf(mcp(stage ="Changepoint"))))

library(tram) ##### Approach 4)
TO<-glht(Colr(MFAP~stage, data=Bracht),linfct = mcp(stage = "Changepoint"))
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